

Conducting Research on English Language Writing Skills amongst MBA Students: A Three-Phase Process

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Abstract: Conducting research on writing skills is a complex process as it involves different steps. These steps occur in different phases including planning, organising and conducting the research study. Consistent efforts are required to complete these phases and achieve success in the process of conducting research on writing skills. Though large numbers of researchers have conducted research on the writing skills, there are very few research articles available to describe the practical aspects of conducting research on writing skills. Therefore, a sincere effort has been made to explain the practical aspects of the writing research process which would also facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the writing skills to the upcoming researchers in this domain.

Keywords: Language, MBA Students, Research, Researching Writing, Writing Skills

JEL Classification Number: I20, I29, M19

1. Introduction

At the commonplace, a language consists of the four basic skills: listening, speaking reading and writing (LSRW). In the context of English Language Teaching (ELT) research is conducted on listening comprehension, speaking skills, reading comprehension, and writing skills. It has been found that research on writing skills is mostly conducted by teachers, educators, and research scholars of the domain. Further, if a teacher shows interest in writing research which involves the process of collecting data from an identified population, he or she has access to their students as the population of their study. On the other hand, the research scholars do not have direct and immediate access to the students in comparison to the teachers. Therefore, the process of conducting research on writing skills becomes challenging to the research scholars because they are confronted with many challenges, and the need to elicit a sense of responsibility towards research, academic honesty and integrity, ethics and contribution to the development of language skills.

The present study is based on the experience of collecting data from the field. The secondary sources have also been applied to analyse the data collected from the field

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which helps to facilitate an argumentative presentation of the research process on writing skills. The analytical method has been employed to describe the steps of conducting research and illustrate the different phases of research on writing skills. The study aims to explore and describe the practical nuances of conducting research on writing skills deliberating on the pertinent research question, how to conduct research on English language writing skills.

2. Conducting Research on Writing Skills

Conducting research on the English language has attracted the attention of educators, scholars, and academicians in the last few decades. Hyland (2016) argues the inclination for research emerges from intersections of theory and practice as a result of the need to illustrate and clarify what scholars do in certain situations and why do they show their interest in research (p.75). “The ways individuals write, the issues they consider when composing, the text they produce, the influence of contexts, purposes and creativity on style, and the strategies writers use to understand writing and improve their practices are all major areas of research” (Hyland, 2016, p.75).

Researching writing is a specialized mechanism. It requires minute observation of the nuances of writing skills in English. Hyland (2003 & 2016) mentions the following significant methods of researching writing:

Questionnaire: It is the method with a focused elicitation of respondents’ reports on actions and attitudes.

Interviews: These are flexible and interactive elicitations by respondents of beliefs and actions.

Focussed Groups: It is one of the specific issues discussed by participants in an interactive group setting.

Tests: The tests are formal elicitation of language samples in constraint conditions.

Verbal Reports: The verbal reports are introspective accounts made during or after composing.

Written Reports: The written reports deal with a diary or log accounts of writing or learning experiences.

Auto-ethnography: This method deals with the self-reflection of researcher’s personal experience.

Observations: observations are direct or recorded data of ‘live’ interactions or writing behaviour.

Text analysis: It is the study of authentic examples of writing from a natural context.

Experiments: The experiment method is a manipulation of a context to study a single feature under controlled conditions.

Case Studies: The case studies are multiple techniques focusing on a single individual or situation.

Ethnographies: Ethnographic method deals with the various techniques to capture the experiences of participants in a situation.

Syntheses: It is a systematic, empirical, and evaluative review of past literature on chosen or a specific topic (p.253); (p.75).

2.1. Need of Conducting Research amongst MBA Students

Language skills play a major role in academics. “Though all skills are necessary for language learning, writing is one of the most important in academic and professional communities” (Bouzar 2021, p.1). Out of these communities, one such community is MBA students and the participants identified for this study are MBA students. The question that arises in the mind of the scholar of this field is ‘Why has the investigator chosen and identified MBA students for the study’? One of the reasons behind researching writing skills is that a survey of ASSOCHAM (Associated Chambers of Commerce & Industry of India) revealed that only 7% of MBA-qualified incumbents from IBS (Indian Business Schools) excluding the top 20 business schools get a job right after completion of their degrees (AEC 2016). The reason identified behind this huge unemployment of MBA-qualified candidates is the lack of employability skills among them. These employability skills are a set of skills in which writing is one of the major skills of communication. Therefore, the MBA students need to instill effective writing skills among themselves to complete their MBA programme effectively and successfully to get better employment opportunities.

Many research scholars of this domain have pointed out this weakness of MBA incumbents in their studies. For instance, Kondal (2019) argues, “It is difficult for students to write effective texts as part of their curriculum for fulfilling future needs” (p.20). In the language classroom, the students have little exposure to business writing and other genres in a professional setting (Kondal, p.20).

2.2. Writing at a Glance

Many linguists have tried to define writing in different ways. Some of them have considered writing as an effective skill rather than putting words on paper. For example, Flower and Hayes (1981) opine “Writing is best understood as a set of distinctive thinking process which writer orchestrate or organize during the act of composing” (p.366). Similarly, Nunan (2003) argues that writing involves both mental and physical activity. In

Nunan's opinion writing is, at its most fundamental level, the physical act of committing ideas or words to a surface, whether it be hieroglyphics written in ink on parchment or an email message entered in a computer (p.88). Moreover, Bouzar (2021) pointed out that writing research has revealed that this skill is extremely complex, as it involves a plethora of processes to produce the final product. It is more than just a representation of ideas; it is the display of multiple processes in which the writer is involved in cognition, problem-solving, and social connection.

2.3. Steps of Writing

Writing is considered as a typical process which involves several steps. Ozonawa states "A typical sequence is comprised of three steps: prewriting, drafting, and, revising. Some sequences, however, use four steps, such as thinking, planning, writing, and editing, while others use five steps, prewriting, drafting, revising, editing, and evaluating" (p.155). The above statement illustrates the flexibility of writers, in the use of different steps while writing. Some of the writers use three steps, others use four and some of them may use five. This leads to the conclusion that different writers use different steps based on their writing requirements and conceptualising of the idea of writing.

3. The Three-Phase Process

The process of conducting research on writing skills can be divided into three major phases. The constituent phases of the process of conducting research include planning, organising and conducting the study.

3.1. Planning

This phase constitutes questions about how to plan and conduct research, and identify the problem, aims and scope and the population. This stage consists of the identification of a research problem which has two major aspects – theoretical and practical aspect. The theoretical aspect deals with the review of related literature, while the practical aspect consists of an identified population which is the locus of conducting research. The target population consists of the participants or respondents who are the source of the data. Further, the participants can be from any segment of the society. In this research study, the MBA students are participants therefore they are the source of primary data, and review of literature makes it easier to analyse the data and present the the process of researching writing skills.

3.2. Organising

Organising consists of selecting an appropriate research design to conduct the study. It also includes designing or selecting a research instrument to collect the data. Research

design is the method of selecting a design on how to collect the data from the field most effectively and economically. It also includes the cost of logistics. A research design consists of a sampling design, statistical design, observational design and operational design (Kothari, 2004 p.39). These four designs (sampling design to select a sample, statistical design to choose the statistical method of analysis, observational design to select the research instrument and operational design for operational procedures) facilitate all four practical aspects of conducting the study. After selecting the research design and the research instrument a researcher has to proceed to the third phase of the study.

3.3. Conducting Study

This is the third phase of the process of conducting research on writing skills. Data collection is the main purpose of this phase. In this phase, the research instrument is administered to the participants to collect the data. The study is conducted in the following steps:

Obtaining Permission from the Institutions to Conduct Research Study: In this phase, the first step is to obtain permission from the institutions to conduct the study. After selecting the population the researcher needs to design informed consent for the participants and the authorities of the institutions. The informed consent states that the identity of the participants will be kept secret, the data collected during the research is used only for the research purpose and their participation in this study is voluntary. It should also be mentioned in the informed consent that the participants have the right to withdraw their participation from the study at any point of time during the study. Generally written permission is granted by the authorities to conduct an empirical research study but this study was conducted during covid-19 hence: the written permission was not sanctioned by the authorities. But the oral permission was granted by the authorities, i.e., the Director of the MBA departments of the institutions to conduct this research study.

Collecting Data: The second step is collecting data. The process of selecting a representative sample of the population is known as sampling design. There are different types of sampling designs. The two major categories of sampling designs are – Probability Sampling or Random Sampling, and Non-probability Sampling. The researcher needs to select a suitable sampling design as per the requirements of the study. After selecting a representative sample, a researcher needs to administer a Pre-test. Based on the Pre-test, candidates of the same level of writing are identified. The next step is to form two groups with these candidates having the same level of writing skills. These groups must be of the same size. One of the groups is called the control group, and the other is called the experimental group. Further, this experimental group is to be exposed to the treatment (pedagogical intervention) while the control group should not be exposed to the treatment. After experimenting, the students of both groups are given a post-test and their answer

scripts are collected. Once the candidates complete this step, it shows that the process of data collection is completed.

Analysing Data and Interpreting Results: This phase deals with the analysis of the data collected through the experiment. The researcher can employ the experimental research design to analyse the data in two ways – a) manually, and b) with the help of the software. To proceed to the data analysis procedure, the researcher needs to evaluate the answer scripts of both the pre-test and post-test and award the marks to each answer script. The awarded marks are subject to the application of statistical procedures or tests to determine the statistical significance.

Presenting Results through the Report: The last step of the conducting study is to present the results obtained through the application of statistical procedures. Therefore, the results are presented in two ways – first, in the form of research papers or research reports, and second, in the form of a dissertation. If the research study deals with an action-research, the results are mostly presented in the form of a research paper or research report. If the research study showcases the fulfilment of an educational degree, it is presented in the form of a dissertation. Thus the researcher uses the results presented in any of the above two forms and draws the conclusion.

4. Conclusion

To sum up it is obvious that the process of conducting research on writing skills has major significance in the field of ELT research. The study demonstrates that the process of researching writing involves complex procedures. These complex procedures are facilitated by the application of different research methods because research methodology plays a significant role in the process of conducting research on writing skills. Therefore, the application of the three-phase model discussed in this research study makes it convenient for a researcher or a scholar to utilise this research process while conducting research in the field of ELT, especially writing skills. Finally, this research study deals with the experimental mode of writing research, therefore, the investigator recommends similar research studies to be conducted on the other modes of writing research.

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